

Association of ACE2 rs2074192 and rs233574 and AGT rs699 Gene Polymorphisms with Obesity and Disease Severity in a Cohort of COVID-19 Affected Syrians

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ABSTRACT

Since the year 2020, accumulating data identified numerous factors playing cardinal roles in inter-individual variations for COVID-19 morbidity including age, obesity, hypertension, comorbidities, in addition to genetic susceptibility. Among the key genes that might contribute to variable clinical outcomes in patients are those involved in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS); namely angiotensin I and II (*ACE*, *ACE2*) and angiotensinogen (*AGT*). In this study, the allele and genotype frequencies of three single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs); *ACE2* rs2074192 and rs233574 in *ACE2* gene, and rs699 in *AGT* gene were recorded in a cohort of Syrian subjects previously suffered from COVID-19 disease with variable symptoms and comorbidities. Fifty four subjects previously inflicted by COVID-19 disease were interviewed and classified based on three categories; according to blood pressure levels [normotensive (NT) or hypertensive (HT)], obesity [lean or overweight and obese (OW/OB)], and COVID-19 conditions [mild or moderate and severe (MOD/SV)]. Genotyping of the three SNPs was performed on DNA extracted from blood samples withdrawn from interviewed subjects followed by electrophoresis and DNA sequencing. We found higher allele frequencies of rs2074192 C allele, rs233574 T allele, and rs699 C allele in OW/OB females (79.2%, 45.2%, and 62.5%, respectively) compared to lean females (33.3%), p values (0.066, 0.079, and 0.043), respectively. Furthermore, the recorded association of higher allele frequencies of the three SNPs with either obesity or COVID-19 severity suggest the C allele for rs2074192, the T allele for *ACE2* rs233574, and the C allele of *AGT* rs699 as risk factors for obesity only in female subjects and COVID-19 severity only in male subjects. Taken together, we proposed two rs2074192-rs233574-rs699 haplotypes, CC-TT-CC in females and C-T-CC in males, as risk haplotypes for COVID-19 severity in our Syrian cohort. Further studies with larger number of COVID-19 affected Syrian subjects should be performed to confirm our preliminary results.

Key Words: Gene polymorphism, *ACE2*, *AGT*, rs2074192, rs233574, rs699, Obesity, COVID-19 severity.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic in recent years conferred a huge burden on health care systems worldwide, as well as intriguing health personnel and scientists who stood obscured with its wide-ranged clinical phenotype in patients, i.e., from regular influenza symptoms to acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and possible death [1,2]. Moreover, the infection with corona virus was accompanied by severe inflammatory and immune responses, represented by a cytokine storm, often leading to severe lung damage and demanding the patient entry into intensive care units (ICUs) and mechanical ventilation at local hospitals [3,4]. The main cellular receptor for corona virus, facilitating viral entry inside cells, is angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (*ACE2*), a cellular receptor and a main component of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), with enzymatic activity that hydrolyzes angiotensin-II (Ang-II) into Ang-1-

7 [5,6]. A second important player in the RAAS system is angiotensinogen (*AGT*), a peptide hormone encoded by the *AGT* gene, which is cleaved by the renin enzyme to produce angiotensin I (Ang-I). The enzyme angiotensin (*ACE* or *ACE1*) then convert Ang-I to Ang-II [7,8]. Ang-II binds to the AT1 receptor, mainly associated with vasoconstriction, fibrosis, inflammation, thrombosis. On the contrary, Ang-1-7, resulting from *ACE2* hydrolysis of Ang-II, binds to the AT2 receptor, resulting in dilation of blood vessels and reduction of fibrosis, inflammation, and thrombosis. Hence, *ACE2* produces a protective response in the lung, while high *ACE* activities is associated with lung and cardiovascular diseases by increasing the activity of the Ang-II/AT1R axis [5,9]. Since the beginning of COVID-19 pandemic, a plethora of scientific reports highlighted the importance of age and several comorbidities, including obesity and hypertension, in worsening the

clinical phenotype in COVID-19 patients, linking the disruption of homeostasis in RAAS, the immune responses, and other physiological systems to severe clinical outcomes [8,10]. Many other reports revealed associations between COVID-19 severity and genetic variants in genes associated with RAAS including *ACE*, *AGT* and *ACE2* [11-15]. Among the key player genes that received lots of attention after the pandemic was the *ACE2* gene. On one hand, many genetic polymorphisms were identified in *ACE2* that could change the binding affinity of the corona virus spike protein, hence, enhancing or decreasing its entry to target cells [12]. On the other hand, and because of *ACE2* major involvement in RAAS regulation, several *ACE2* gene polymorphisms were identified and linked to predisposing COVID-19 patients to comorbidities that could worsen their clinical path [16,17]. One intronic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) in *ACE2*, rs2074192, has been linked to hypertension and severity of COVID-19 [18-21]. Another intronic SNP in *ACE2* gene, rs233574, has been linked to stability of *ACE2* mRNA and protein [22,23]. Moreover, few reports identified an exonic SNP in the *AGT* gene, rs699 or M268T, which replaces methionine residue with threonine in the angiotensinogen peptide and was showed to be associated with increased susceptibility to COVID-19 [7,24]. Nevertheless, it appeared that the effects of the aforementioned three SNPs in *ACE2* and *AGT* genes on COVID-19 severity were correlated to the studied population ethnicities, as data linked to the involvement of these SNPs in COVID-19 morbidities and co-morbidities often came contradictory, taking into consideration the varied allelic frequencies among different ethnic groups. Hence, in this report, we studied the association of the two SNPs in *ACE2* gene, rs2074192 and rs233574, in addition to the *AGT* rs699 SNP, with COVID-19 disease severity in a cohort of Syrian patients whose corona virus infection was previously confirmed by standard methods. We reported the allele, genotype and haplotype frequencies of the three polymorphisms in both genders after categorizing patients according to obesity, hypertension and COVID-19 severity

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects and Samples

Our retrospective cohort study included 54, 24 females and 30 males, non-related participants with previously confirmed COVID-19 positive disease, by PCR positive tests (22 cases) or positive chest X-ray in addition to clinical symptoms (22 cases) or positive Corona IgG (10 cases). Study cases were classified based on 3 categories; blood pressure into

(39 normotensive NT) and (15 hypertensive HT); obesity, reflected by body mass index (BMI), into (20 lean, BMI<25) and (34 overweight OW, 25<BMI<30 and obese OB, BMI>30); and finally COVID-19 status into (21 mild cases, mild symptoms) and (33 moderate cases including 17 with intense symptoms but oxygenation level >94, and 13 severe cases with intense symptoms, and 3 cases with life threatening conditions and oxygenation level <94). Our study was approved by both the Bioethics Committee at the Faculty of Pharmacy - Damascus University, and the National Committee for Ethics of Scientific Research and Novel Technologies (CONEST), at the Higher Commission for Scientific Research. Informed consents were obtained from all subjects prior to their enrollment. Three milliliters of peripheral blood were collected on Ethylene Diamine Tetra-acetic Acid (EDTA) and stored at -20 °C

DNA Isolation and Amplification

Molecular work and genotyping processes were performed at the pharmaceutical biotechnology and immunology laboratories- National Commission for Biotechnology, Damascus, except for DNA sequencing. Genomic DNA was isolated from blood samples using Qiagen blood DNA extraction kit (Qiagen, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. DNA concentrations and purity were assessed using Nano drop (Maestrogen®, Taiwan). The extracted DNA quality was verified by horizontal 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis, followed by gel staining with ethidium bromide staining (Promega®, USA), and gel documentation (Cleaver, UK). We performed polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification using two sets of specific primer pairs. For both *ACE2* rs2074192 and rs233574 we used forward primer 5` CAGCAAAGGGGACACTTAGACA 3` and reverse primer 5` AGCCATTCCCATCCAGTG 3`, with a theoretical expected amplicon size of 707 base pair (bp). For *AGT* rs699, we used forward primer 5` GTGGTCACCAGGTATGTCCG 3` and reverse primer 5` TATACCCCTGTGGTCC TCCC 3`, with an expected amplicon size of 291 base pair (bp). All primers were manufactured by (Eurofins, Belgium), and were designed using Primer 3 software tool and checked prior to ordering using the MFE primer bioinformatics tool (<https://mfepimer3.igenetech.com/spec>) to evade any non-specific binding to genomic DNA. PCR was performed according to standard methods using thermal cycler (SENSEQUEST®, Germany) and 2X Master Mix (Genedirex®, Taiwan). The PCR reaction mixture contained 20 ng of genomic DNA and 0.25 µm/l of each primer. PCR amplification was performed according the following protocol including: initial denaturation for 5 min at 95° C, 35 cycles of (30 sec at 94° C, 30 sec at 57°

C, and 1 min at 72° C), and a final 10 min at 72° C for final extension. PCR amplicons were analyzed by agarose gel electrophoresis, using an electrophoresis apparatus from (Clever, UK) and a 100 bp DNA size marker from (Genedirex®, Taiwan). DNA Sequencing was performed at (Macrogen, South Korea) according to standard protocols

Bioinformatics & Statistical Analyses

Sequencing chromatograms were analyzed using bioinformatics tool (Geneious® software, USA). Genotype frequencies of sample alleles were estimated by gene counting method. Statistical analyses were performed using chi-square calculator <https://www.socscistatistics.com/tests/> to compare the ratios of the allele and genotype frequencies, respectively, with a p-value <0.05 as significant. Finally, EXCEL T test calculator was used to compare means of age and BMI among study cases, with a p-value <0.05 for statistical significance

RESULTS

Subjects

No significant differences were recorded concerning age and body mass index (BMI) of females and males, (Table 1). When dividing subjects according to blood pressure conditions and classifying them as NT and HT groups however, both age and BMI were significantly higher in HT (40 yrs. and 36.8 kg/m²) compared to NT (46.7 yrs. 29.7 kg/m²), respectively, (Table 1). Additionally, overweight (OW) and obese (OB) subjects showed significantly higher mean of age (49.6 yrs.) compared to lean subjects (age 34.4 yrs.). Finally, subjects with moderate or severe COVID-19 conditions (MOD/SV) were significantly older compared to those with mild conditions (48.5 versus 36.6 yrs., respectively), while no significant difference appeared in BMI between MOD/SV and mild

Genotyping

Amplification of *ACE2* and *AGT* gene sequences was successful, with amplicons appeared with expected molecular weights (MW), ~ 700 bp for *ACE2* and between 200 and 300 bp for *AGT*, (Fig. 1 a). For all three SNPs, homozygotes and heterozygotes were easily identified by reading the sequencing chromatograms; (GG/CC, AA/TT, or AG/TC) for rs699, (CC, CT, or TT) for rs2074192, and (TT, CC, or CT) for rs233574, (Fig. 1, b-d)

Allele Frequencies

After reading all sequencing chromatograms, alleles for all three SNPs were counted and recorded for either females or males included in either of three categories; blood pressure, obesity, and COVID-19 condition. Of note, and since *ACE2* gene occurs on X chromosome whereas *AGT* occurs on an autosome, for both rs2074192 and rs233574

we counted two alleles for females but only one allele in males, while for rs699 we counted the two alleles for both females and males. Table 2 shows the number of alleles in females and males recorded for each of the three SNPs, and according to the distribution of the study subjects across the three categories. The only recorded significant difference was in rs699 when comparing T and C allele frequencies between lean versus OW/OB females, where C allele was significantly higher in OW/OB compared to lean females, p=0.043. Noteworthy, higher rs699 C allele frequency was recorded in HT compared to NT female subject, higher rs2074192 C allele frequency was recorded in OW/OB compared to lean subjects, higher rs233574 C allele frequency was recorded in lean compared to OW/OB subjects, and higher rs2074192 C allele frequency was recorded in both female and male subjects with MOD/SV compared to mild COVID-19 conditions, although neither comparison attained significance, p>0.05

Genotype Frequencies

Genotypes were counted and recorded for all three SNPs. In all three categories, no significant differences were detected vis-à-vis genotype frequencies among NT and HT, lean and OW/OB, or mild and MOD/SV phenotypes. Fig 2 shows genotype frequencies in the COVID-19 condition category for rs699 in both females and males, while showing genotype frequencies only in females for rs2074192 and rs233574. Since *ACE2* occurs on X-chromosome, genotypes for either rs2074192 or rs233574 in males are the same as allele frequencies shown in Table 2. Of note; rs2074192 CC genotype appeared in 7 out of 14 female subject with MOD/SV condition (50%) compared to 3 out of 10 female subjects (30%) with mild condition; rs699 CC genotype appeared in 3 out of 14 female subjects with MOD/SV condition (21.5%) while no female had this genotype in the mild condition population; and finally the rs699 TC genotype appeared in 9 out of 19 male subjects with MOD/SV condition (47.4%) while it only appeared in 1 male out of 11 male subjects (9.1%) with mild condition

Haplotype Frequencies

Distribution of possible haplotypes including rs2074192, rs233574, and rs699 in either female or male subjects were counted and their frequencies recorded (Tables 3 & 4). Table 3 shows haplotype frequencies when taking only two SNPs separately; i.e., rs2074192 and rs699, or rs2074192 and rs233574, while Table 4 shows haplotype frequencies for all three SNPs together

***ACE2* rs2074192 - *AGT* rs699 Haplotypes**

Table 3(a) shows all possible 9 haplotypes (3²) for females and all 6 haplotypes for males.

In females, the most common haplotype when considering both rs2074192 and rs699 polymorphisms was CC-TC, respectively. Among the three categories, the highest difference in haplotype frequencies was detected for TC-TC haplotype between lean (16.7%) and OW/OB (41.7%) groups. The TT-CC haplotype was not recorded in female subjects. In males, the highest recorded haplotype for rs2074192

and rs699 was C-CC, respectively. Moreover, 6 out of 19 male subjects with MOD/SV condition had the C-TC haplotype, while no males out of 11 were recorded with this haplotype in male subjects with mild conditions. Similarly, 3 OW/OB male subjects had the C-TT haplotype, while no lean males were recorded with this haplotype

Table 1: Comparison between study subjects classified based on gender, blood pressure, obesity, and COVID-19 severity.

Categories (No. subjects)	Age (Mean ± STD)	P value	BMI (Mean ± STD)	P value
Females (24)	40.4 ± 17.2	ns	26.0 ± 4.7	ns
Males (30)	46.7 ± 17.4		27.8 ± 4.3	
NT (39)	36.8 ± 13.2	P<0.001	25.9 ± 4.1	P<0.01
HT (15)	62.3 ± 13.3		29.7 ± 4.7	
Lean (20)	34.1 ± 11.9	P<0.01	22.6 ± 2.2	P<0.001
OW/OB (34)	49.6 ± 17.7		29.6 ± 3.4	
Mild (21)	36.6 ± 12.3	P<0.05	27.1 ± 4.1	ns
MOD/SV (33)	48.5 ± 18.7		26.9 ± 4.8	

ns: not significant (p>0.05); NT: normotensive, HT: hypertensive; OW/OB: overweight or obese; MOD/SV: moderate or severe. STD: standard deviation. BMI: Body mass index.

Fig. 1 Amplification and genotyping of AGT and ACE2 amplicons. a) Gel electrophoresis showing two amplicons, one with size between 200 and 300 bp (for AGT), and the other close to 700 bp (for ACE2). B-d) Sequencing chromatograms of rs699, rs2074192, and rs233574, respectively, with arrows pointing to the polymorphism site

Table 2: Comparison of Allelic frequencies in female and male subjects classified according based on three categories; blood pressure, obesity, and COVID-19 condition.							
Category 1: Blood Pressure							
SNP		Females			Males		
		NT (No = 18)	HT (No = 6)	p value	NT (No = 21)	HT (No = 9)	p value
rs2074192	T	15 (41.7%)	3 (25%)	0.302	8 (38.1%)	3 (33.3%)	0.804
	C	21 (58.3%)	9 (75%)		13 (61.9%)	6 (66.7%)	
rs233574	T	14 (38.9%)	6 (50%)	0.498	9 (42.9%)	5 (55.6%)	0.523
	C	22 (61.1%)	6 (50%)		12 (57.1%)	4 (44.4%)	
rs699	T	22 (61.1%)	4 (33.3%)	0.094	19 (45.2%)	7 (38.9%)	0.649
	C	14 (38.9%)	8 (66.7%)		23 (54.8%)	11 (61.1%)	
Category 2: Obesity							
SNP		Females			Males		
		Lean (No = 12)	OW/OB (No = 12)	p value	Lean (No = 8)	OW/OB (No = 22)	p value
rs2074192	T	11 (45.8%)	5 (20.8%)	0.066	3 (37.5%)	8 (36.4%)	0.201
	C	13 (54.2%)	19 (79.2%)		5 (62.5%)	14 (63.6%)	
rs233574	T	7 (29.2%)	13 (54.2%)	0.079	3 (37.5%)	10 (45.5%)	0.697
	C	17 (70.8%)	11 (45.8%)		5 (62.5%)	12 (54.5%)	
rs699	T	16 (66.7%)	9 (37.5%)	0.043	5 (31.3%)	21 (47.7%)	0.255
	C	8 (33.3%)	15 (62.5%)		11 (68.7%)	23 (52.3%)	
Category 3: COVID Condition							
SNP		Females			Males		
		Mild (No = 10)	MOD/SV (No = 14)	p value	Mild (No = 11)	MOD/SV (No = 19)	p value
rs2074192	T	10 (50%)	8 (28.6%)	0.13	6 (54.5%)	5 (26.3%)	0.122
	C	10 (50%)	20 (71.4%)		5 (45.5%)	14 (73.7%)	
rs233574	T	8 (40%)	12 (42.9%)	0.843	5 (45.5%)	8 (42.1%)	0.858
	C	12 (60%)	16 (57.1%)		6 (54.5%)	11 (57.9%)	
rs699	T	13 (65%)	12 (42.9%)	0.13	9 (40.9%)	17 (44.7%)	0.773
	C	7 (35%)	16 (57.1%)		13 (59.1%)	21 (55.3%)	
NT: normotensive, HT: hypertensive; OW/OB: overweight or obese; MOD/SV: moderate or severe.							

Fig 2. Distribution of genotype frequencies within COVID-19 category for rs2074192 and rs233574 only in females, and for rs699 in both females and males. Figures within orange bars represent number of individuals in the mild groups, while figures on top of blue bars represent number of individuals in the moderate (MOD) or severe (SV) groups. ns: not significant

ACE2 rs2074192 - ACE2 rs233574 Haplotypes

Table 3(b) shows all possible 9 haplotypes (3²) for females and all 4 haplotypes for males. In females, the most common haplotype when considering both rs2074192 and rs233574 genotypes was TC-TC, respectively. In addition, 4 females (33.3%) had the CC-TT haplotype in the OW/OB groups, while no females had this haplotype in the lean group. Reversibly, 3 females (25%) had the CC-TC haplotype in the lean groups, while no females had this haplotype in the OW/OB group. In males, the highest recorded haplotype was C-T. Moreover, the highest difference among haplotype frequencies was detected for C-C haplotype in mild (1 male, 9.1%) and MOD/SV (6 males, 31.6%) groups

ACE2 rs2074192 - ACE2 rs233574 – AGT rs699 Haplotypes

Table 4 shows the recorded 12 haplotypes out of the 27 (3³) possible haplotypes in females and 9 recorded haplotypes out of 12 possible haplotypes for males. In females, the most frequent haplotype among the three categories was TC-TC-TC. In addition, 3 females (25%) in the OW/OB group showed the CC-TT-TC haplotype, while no females showed this haplotype in the lean group. Contrariwise, 3 females (16.7%) in the NT group showed the CC-TT-TC haplotype, while no females showed this haplotype in the HT group. One female had the haplotype CC-TT-CC in all three HT, OW/OB and MOD/SV groups. Of note, 15 possible haplotypes were absent in females including TT-CC-TT. In males, the highest recorded haplotype in the three categories was C-T-CC. In addition, the highest differences among haplotype frequencies were detected for C-T-TC and T-C-TC haplotypes,

where 4 males (21%) in the MOD/SV groups have C-T-TC in comparison with none in the mild groups, and 3 males (15.8%) in the MOD/SV groups have T-C-TC in comparison with none in the mild groups. Finally, among the MOD/SV group, three females aged (55, 76 and 86), and with BMI (25, 34, and 26) had a life threatening conditions that demanded their entry into ICU at a local hospital. The haplotypes of the four subjects were (TC-TC-TC), (CC-CC-TC), (CC-TT-CC)

DISCUSSION

Age, Obesity, and Gender in Study Subjects

We recorded no significant differences in mean age or BMI between the 24 females and the 30 males included in this study. However, normotensive subjects were clearly younger and leaner compared to hypertensive subjects (Table 1). In fact, aging and obesity are well known to be independent risk factors for raising blood pressure levels [25,26]. Moreover, overweight occurring at younger age at onset was reported to be associated with significantly increased risk of hypertension with the highest relative risk among individuals with 18–39 years of age at onset of overweight [27]. As for COVID-19 severity, subjects with moderate and severe conditions were significantly older but not more obese than those with mild conditions (Table 1). In fact, the severity of COVID-19 is known to be associated with specific pre-existing conditions including age, sex, obesity, hypertension and genetic susceptibility, with mortalities occurs mostly in the elderly and is about double in males compared to females [18,28]. Although no significant difference in BMI was found between subjects with mild compared to MOD/SV conditions (Table 1), it is noteworthy that 22 out of 30 males (73.3%) and 12

Table 3: Frequencies of either (rs2074192-rs699) or (2074192-rs233574) haplotypes recorded in females and males after classifying the study subjects according to three categories; blood pressure, obesity, and COVID-19 conditions.

Females (n=24)		Blood Pressure		Obesity		COVID-19 conditions	
		NT	HT	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
1	CC-CC	----	1 (16.7%)	----	1 (8.3%)	----	1 (7.1%)
2	CC-TC	6 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	4 (33.3%)	4 (33.3%)	3 (30%)	5 (35.7%)
3	CC-TT	1 (5.5%)	----	1 (8.3%)	----	----	1 (7.1%)
4	TC-CC	1 (5.5%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (8.3%)	2 (16.7%)	----	2 (14.2%)
5	TC-TC	5 (27.8%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (16.7%)	5 (41.7%)	3 (30%)	4 (28.6%)
6	TC-TT	1 (5.5%)	----	----	----	1 (10%)	----
7	TT-CC	----	----	----	----	----	----
8	TT-TC	2 (11%)	----	2 (16.7%)	----	1 (10%)	1 (7.1%)
9	TT-TT	2 (11%)	----	2 (16.7%)	----	2 (20%)	----
Total		18	6	12	12	10	14

Males (n=30)		Blood Pressure		Obesity		COVID-19 conditions	
		NT	HT	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
1	C-CC	6 (28.6%)	4 (44.4%)	3 (37.5%)	7 (31.8%)	4 (36.4%)	6 (31.6%)
2	C-TC	5 (23.8%)	1 (11.1%)	2 (25%)	4 (18.2%)	----	6 (31.6%)
3	C-TT	2 (9.5%)	1 (11.1%)	----	3 (13.6%)	1 (9%)	2 (10.5%)
4	T-CC	2 (9.5%)	----	1 (12.5%)	1 (4.5%)	2 (18%)	----
5	T-TC	2 (9.5%)	2 (22.2%)	1 (12.5%)	3 (13.6%)	1 (9%)	3 (15.8%)
6	T-TT	4 (19%)	1 (11.1%)	1 (12.5%)	4 (18.2%)	3 (27.3%)	2 (10.5%)
Total		21	9	8	22	11	19

Females (n=24)		Blood Pressure		Obesity		COVID-19 conditions	
		NT	HT	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
1	CC-CC	2 (11.1%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (16.7%)	1 (8.3%)	1 (10%)	2 (14.3%)
2	CC-TC	2 (11.1%)	1 (16.7%)	3 (25%)	----	1 (10%)	2 (14.3%)
3	CC-TT	3 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	----	4 (33.3%)	1 (10%)	3 (21.4%)
4	TC-CC	3 (16.7%)	----	1 (8.3%)	2 (16.7%)	1 (10%)	2 (14.3%)
5	TC-TC	4 (22.2%)	3 (50%)	2 (16.7%)	5 (41.7%)	3 (30%)	4 (28.6%)
6	TC-TT	----	----	----	----	----	----
7	TT-CC	2 (11.1%)	----	2 (16.7%)	----	1 (10%)	1 (7.1%)
8	TT-TC	2 (11.1%)	----	2 (16.7%)	----	2 (20%)	----
9	TT-TT	----	----	----	----	----	----
Total		18	6	12	12	10	14

Males (n=30)		Blood Pressure		Obesity		COVID-19 condition	
		NT	HT	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
1	C-C	4 (19%)	3 (33.3%)	2 (25%)	5 (22.7%)	1 (9.1%)	6 (31.6%)
2	C-T	9 (42.9%)	3 (33.3%)	3 (37.5%)	9 (40.9%)	4 (36.3%)	8 (42.1%)
3	T-C	8 (38.1%)	2 (22.2%)	3 (37.5%)	7 (31.8%)	5 (45.5%)	5 (26.3%)
4	T-T	----	1 (11.1%)	----	1 (4.6%)	1 (9.1%)	----
Total		21	9	8	22	11	19

NT: normotensive, HT: hypertensive; OW/OB: overweight or obese; MOD/SV: moderate or severe.

Table 4: Haplotype frequencies of three SNPS (rs2074192-rs233574-rs699) recorded in females and males after classifying the study subjects according to three categories; blood pressure, obesity, and COVID-19 condition.

Females		Blood Pressure		Obesity		COVID-19 conditions	
		NT	HT	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
1	CC-CC-TC	2 (11%)	1 (16.6%)	2 (16.6%)	1 (8.3%)	1 (10%)	2 (14.3%)
2	CC-TC-TT	1 (5.6%)	----	1 (8.3%)	----	----	1 (7.1%)
3	CC-TC-TC	1 (5.6%)	1 (16.6%)	2 (16.6%)	----	1 (10%)	1 (7.1%)
4	CC-TT-CC	----	1 (16.6%)	----	1 (8.3%)	----	1 (7.1%)
5	CC-TT-TC	3 (16.7%)	----	----	3 (25%)	1 (10%)	2 (14.3%)
6	TC-CC-CC	1 (5.6%)	----	----	1 (8.3%)	----	1 (7.1%)
7	TC-CC-TC	1 (5.6%)	----	----	----	----	1 (7.1%)
8	TC-CC-TT	1 (5.6%)	----	1 (8.3%)	----	1 (10%)	----
9	TC-TC-CC	----	1 (16.6%)	----	1 (8.3%)	----	1 (7.1%)
10	TC-TC-TC	4 (22%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (16.6%)	4 (33.3%)	3 (30%)	3 (21.4%)
11	TT-CC-TC	2 (11%)	----	2 (16.6%)	1 (8.3%)	1 (10%)	1 (7.1%)
12	TT-TC-TT	2 (11%)	----	2 (16.6%)	----	2 (20%)	----
Total		18	6	12	12	10	14

Males		Blood Pressure		Obesity		COVID-19 conditions	
		NT	HT	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
1	C-C-CC	----	2 (22%)	1 (12.5%)	1 (4.5%)	----	2 (10.5%)
2	C-C-TC	2 (9.5%)	----	1 (12.5%)	1 (4.5%)	----	2 (10.5%)
3	C-C-TT	2 (9.5%)	1 (11%)	----	3 (13.6%)	1 (9%)	2 (10.5%)
4	C-T-CC	6 (28.6%)	2 (22%)	2 (25%)	6 (27.3%)	4 (36.4%)	4 (21%)
5	C-T-TC	3 (14.3%)	1 (11%)	1 (12.5%)	3 (13.6%)	----	4 (21%)
6	T-C-CC	2 (9.5%)	----	1 (12.5%)	1 (4.5%)	2 (18%)	----
7	T-C-TC	2 (9.5%)	1 (11%)	1 (12.5%)	2 (9%)	----	3 (15.8%)
8	T-C-TT	4 (19%)	1 (11%)	1 (12.5%)	4 (18.2%)	3 (27.3%)	2 (10.5%)
9	T-T-TC	----	1 (11%)	----	1 (4.5%)	1 (9%)	----
Total		21	9	8	22	11	19

NT: normotensive, HT: hypertensive; OW/OB: overweight or obese; MOD/SV: moderate or severe.

out of 24 females (50%) were overweight or obese (Table 2). This made the majority of subjects enrolled in this study as OW/OB, with mean BMI in this group (26.9 kg/m²) already in the overweight range, and probably justifies the absence of differences in BMI between subjects with mild and MOD/SV COVID-19 conditions. Of note, no differences were found regarding gender distribution after classification of study subjects according to blood pressure and COVID-19 severity (Table 2); females (NT 75%, HT 25%; Mild 41.7%, MOD/SV 58.3%) and males (NT 70%, HT 30%; Mild 36.7%, MOD/SV 63.3%)

ACE2 rs2074192 C>T

The rs2074192 polymorphism is a variation of intron 16 in ACE2 gene located on X chromosome, with global C allele frequency around 56.9% and T allele frequency around 43.1%, European (C 55.3%, T 44.7%), African (C 68.4%, T 31.6%), and Asian (C

57.9%, T 42.1%), (www.snpedia.com). Pouladi and Abdolahi showed *in silico* a major effect of this SNP on the secondary structure of ACE2 RNA [23], suggesting a possible dysregulating of ACE2 transcription or translation and protein stability, and leading to a decrease in SARS-CoV-2 viral entry. In fact, many previous reports recorded an association, although controversial, between rs2074192 with hypertension and COVID-19 severity [11,17,19,20,29]. In Chinese population, Luo *et al.*, demonstrated that rs2074192 T allele was associated with essential hypertension in Chinese patients [11]. Moreover, Pan *et al.*, reported that individuals with TC or TT genotype were associated with essential hypertension [29]. Sheikhian *et al.*, showed that ACE2 rs2074192 TT genotype was associated with the COVID-19 mortality in Iranian COVID-19 patients [20]. On the contrary, Martinez-Gomez *et al.* in Mexican

patients reported higher C allele frequency and CC genotype frequency in COVID-19 patients with severe and critical conditions [17]. Similarly, Molina *et al.*, showed the T allele to be protective against COVID-19 severity in a cohort of Italian patients [19]. These previous reports highlight the differences in genetic composition among different ethnicities and raise the importance of examining SNP distribution among other population, including Syrians. Despite the fact that no significant differences were found in the current study when comparing rs2074192 allelic and genotypic frequencies between female and male subjects, the data suggest a modest association between the C allele with hypertension, obesity and COVID-19 severity as allele frequencies were higher in hypertensive females compared to normotensive peers (p value = 0.3), in OW/OB females compared to lean subjects (p value = 0.066), and in female and male subjects with MOD/SV conditions compared to those with mild conditions (p value = 0.13, and 0.12, respectively) (Table 2). In addition, the CC genotype frequency was higher in female subjects with MOD/SV compared to those with mild conditions (Fig 2). These data agree with a protective effect of T allele possibly by decreasing the effect of ACE2 enzyme that hydrolyzes Ang-II and prevents the latter's contribution to vasoconstriction, fibrosis, inflammation, and thrombosis [8], whereas the C allele or CC genotype might be considered as risk factors

ACE2 rs233574 T>C

The rs233574 polymorphism is an intronic variation in ACE2 gene on X-chromosome, with global T allele frequency around 51.8% and C allele frequency around 48.2%, European (T 50.5%, C 49.5%), African (T 69.1%, C 30.9%), and Asian (T 30%, C 70%), (www.snpedia.com). Similar to rs2074192, the rs233574 theoretically affects the RNA secondary structure possibly leading to destabilizing ACE2 transcript and protein [22,23]. Nevertheless, the T reference allele can additionally enhance the affinity for binding ETR-3 splicing factor, thus increasing susceptibility for COVID-19 [30]. Interestingly, most ethnic populations have comparably mid or low C allele frequency, while its frequency in Chinese population could reach 70%, hence this allele could have been played its protective role on a large number of Chinese COVID-19 patients, although no clinical data available supporting the protective role of rs233574. Likewise, data from our study might support a protective effect for C allele while the T allele being a risk factor. In fact, higher T allele frequencies were detected in hypertensive females (50%) and males (55.6%) compared to normotensive peers (38.9% and 42.9%, respectively),

although with no significance (p value > 0.05), and in OW/OB compared to lean female subjects (p value = 0.079), while very similar C and T allele frequencies were found in female and male subjects with MOD/SV compared to those with mild conditions (p value = 0.85) (Table 2). Finally, the TT genotype frequency was higher in female subjects with MOD/SV compared to those with mild conditions (Fig 2)

AGT rs699 T>C

This polymorphism occurs on exon 2 in AGT gene on chromosome 1, leading to replacement of methionine residue with threonine in the 268 position within the primary protein structure, with global T allele frequency around 54.5% and C allele frequency around 45.5%, European (T 57.9%, C 42.1%), African (T 18.1%, C 81.9%), and Asian (T 17.5%, C 82.5%), (www.snpedia.com). In fact, it was reported that rs699 C allele was associated with increased plasma angiotensinogen levels, leading to hypertension [7]. Several previous reports showed a significant rs699 association with hypertension and/or COVID-19 severity [24,31-35]. Specifically; Mirahmadi *et al.*, found that rs699 C allele is a predisposing variant for coronary artery disease (CAD) in the Iranian population [32]; Repchuk *et al.*, found that rs699 C allele was associated with 2.5 fold elevation of systolic and diastolic BP in Ukrainian patients [33]; Yako *et al.*, found an association between rs699 and hypertension in Tunisian and South African patients [34]; Cafiero *et al.*, found higher allele C (45%) and CC genotype (22%) frequencies in symptomatic compared to asymptomatic (C 31%, CC 0%) Italian COVID-19 patients [31]; and Kouhpayeh *et al.*, demonstrated that the TC genotype and C allele of AGT rs699 increased the risk of COVID-19 infection in Iranian COVID-19 patients [24]. Finally, Khamlaoui *et al.*, found that rs699 was associated with high BMI, waist circumference and overweight-obesity [35]. Data from our current study demonstrated the presence of higher rs699 C allele frequency in hypertensive compared to normotensive, OW/OB compared to lean, and MOD/SV compared to mild COVID-19, although with larger differences in females compared to males, and reaching significance only when comparing OW/OB with lean females, p=0.034, (Table 2). In addition, the CC genotype appeared in 3 females in the MOD/SV group compared to none in the Mild groups (Fig 2). Hence, one could extrapolate from these data the rs699 C as a risk allele while T as a protective allele related to COVID-19 severity. Notably, all subjects included in our study were inflicted by COVID-19, although with a range of symptoms. Hence, comparing allele frequencies

in our subjects for all three SNPs with those previously reported in different ethnicities and populations would be probably imprecise, especially when taking into account the large differences in allele frequencies among different populations, as in the case of rs233574 and rs699. Nevertheless, when considering the allele frequencies values in normotensive female subjects (Table 2), we could find out similar allelic frequencies of rs2074192 to those in most ethnicities, similar allelic frequencies of rs233574 to those in Asians but not Europeans and Africans, and slightly higher allelic frequencies of rs699 compared to those in Europeans but soundly different from their frequencies in Africans and Asians. In fact, deviation of allelic frequency in the Syrian population documented in this study is not surprising taking into consideration the geographical location of Syria amid the three continents, where the genetic composition of Syrians is expected to be unique compared to most other population because of migration and breeding inflected by several factors during thousands of years. Nonetheless, a future study reporting allelic frequencies of all three SNPs in healthy Syrian controls would result in accurate estimates on SNP frequencies. On the other hand, it was interesting to note that the differences in allelic frequencies for all three SNPs were significant or close to significance with small p values, only when comparing these frequencies in the obesity but not in blood pressure and COVID-19 condition categories; specifically, between lean and OW/OB female subjects (Table 2). In fact, it is very well documented that visceral obesity is a risk factor for cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome, hypercoagulability and vitamin D deficiency, all are hallmarks for COVID-19 severity [15,36,37]. Recently, Steenblock *et al.*, identified several factors involved in the mechanism by which obesity affects COVID-19 outcome, including physical stress on ventilation, increased risk of pulmonary fibrosis, impairment of the immune system and accumulation of macrophages in adipose tissues, increasing adiponectin levels that can stimulate macrophages production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6 and IL-1 β , and finally activating the RAAS leading to increased blood pressure, atherosclerosis and thrombosis [38]. One could postulate that possible effects of rs2074192, rs233574, and rs699 on either blood pressure levels and/or COVID-19 severity could be occurring via indirect involvement of obesity-dependent biochemical pathways. This could be

further tested on a large number of individuals who suffered from severe COVID-19 disease. Equally remarkable, are the sound differences in allele frequency profiles for all three SNPs between females and males within the obesity category (Table 2), in addition to different distribution of rs699 genotypes between females and males within COVID-19 category (Fig 2). Actually, similar differences were previously reported not only for X-linked gene polymorphisms, but even for genes located on autosomes. For example, Hamet *et al.*, showed that the T allele of rs2074192 was associated with hypertension only in obese males, while reporting a significant interaction with obesity of another SNP in the ACE2 gene, rs233575, but only in females [18]. On the other hand, Repchuk *et al.*, showed that rs699 C allele was associated with high systolic and diastolic blood pressure only in females [33]. As a matter of fact, gender related genotype-phenotype interactions is highly complicated and was previously tackled by many researchers. Indeed, endocrine status, in addition to genetic composition, vitally affects phenotypes and could be influenced by several factors including differences in hormonal levels and even lifestyle habits, such as smoking and alcohol consumption, etc., [39-41]

Haplotypes

Similar to the aforementioned differences in allelic and genotypic frequencies among females and males, distribution of haplotypes varied between the two genders (Tables 3 & 4). This was clear in the different distribution of most common haplotypes in females and males; for rs2079142-rs699, CC-TC in females, and C-CC in males; for rs2079142-rs233574, TC-TC in females and C-T in males; and for rs2079142-rs233574-rs699, TC-TC-TC in females and C-T-CC in males. This surely could contribute to phenotypic differences between the two genders, and explain the distinct association of certain alleles, genotypes, and haplotypes with blood pressure, obesity, and COVID-19 severity. Table 5 summarizes the clearest differences in haplotype distribution among the two genders demonstrated in Tables 3 and 4. Reviewing Table 5 highlights one important finding, i.e., the association of different haplotypes with obesity only in female but not in male subjects, whereas other haplotypes were associated with COVID-19 conditions only in male but not in female subjects. Once again, this eludes to the disparity between the two genders as for the genetic composition and its phenotypic effects. Several preliminary conclusions might be extrapolated from Table 5; the rs2074192 CC genotype is probably associated with obesity in females; the rs699 TC genotype is probably not

associated with either obesity or COVID-19 severity, since it was commonly distributed among females and males; the rs233574 TT or TC genotypes are probably associated with obesity; the rs2074192 C allele is associated with obesity in females and COVID-19 severity in males, while the rs2074192 T allele could be protective. Nonetheless, further studies should be performed to check for the

validity of these proposals. Lastly, two haplotypes were overrepresented in the HT compared to NT subjects (Table 3); the rs2074192-rs699 C-CC haplotype in males, the rs2074192-rs233574 TC-TC haplotype in females. In both cases, this could be due to the presence of the rs2074192 C allele that has been reported to be previously associated with hypertension in COVID-19 patients [17,19]

Table 5: Most demonstrated differences in haplotype distribution between female and male subjects.

Haplotype	G	Lean	OW/OB	Mild	MOD/SV
TC-TC (rs2074192-rs699)	F	L (16.7%)	H (41.7%)		
CC-TT (rs2074192-rs233574)	F	L (0%)	H (33.3%)		
CC-TC (rs2074192-rs233574)	F	H (25%)	L (0%)		
CC-TT-TC (rs2074192-rs233574-rs699)	F	L (0%)	H (25%)		
<hr/>					
C-TC (rs2074192-rs699)	M			L (0%)	H (31.6%)
C-C (rs2074192-rs233574)	M			L (9.1%)	H (31.6%)
T-C (rs2074192-rs233574)	M			H (45.5%)	L (26.3%)
C-T-TC (rs2074192-rs233574-rs699)	M			L (0%)	H (21%)

G: gender, F: females, M: males, L: lower, H: higher, OW/OB: overweight or obese; MOD/SV: moderate or severe.

Taken together, and suggesting that the rs2074192 C allele, the rs233574 T allele, and the rs699 C allele, as risk alleles for COVID-19 morbidity and/or comorbidities, one could hypothesize the most risky haplotype to be CC-TT-CC in females, and C-T-CC in males, while the most protective haplotype to be TT-CC-TT in females, and T-C-TT in males. Indeed, the fact that we recorded only 12 out of 27 possible haplotypes in our female population (Table 4), while the rest 15 unfound haplotypes included the TT-CC-TT haplotype might support our proposed haplotype functional classification. On the contrary, life threatening cases could have haplotypes identical or similar to the risky haplotypes we proposed. In fact, three cases in our study population had life threatening conditions demanding them to enter the ICU at local hospitals. The haplotypes of these three female subjects were (TC-TC-TC), (CC-CC-TC), (CC-TT-CC), i.e., one identical and two close haplotypes to the proposed most risky haplotype CC-TT-CC. Nonetheless, the three female subjects were elderly with ages (55, 76 and 86) and BMI (25, 34, and 26), so it is not possible to isolate the possible effect of age on COVID-19 severity in these individuals

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the allele, genotype and haplotype frequencies of three single nucleotide polymorphisms, ACE2 rs2074192, ACE2 rs233574,

and AGT rs699 were recorded in a cohort of Syrian subjects previously suffered from COVID-19 disease with variable symptoms and comorbidities. We found significant association between rs699 and obesity in the female subject, while the other two SNPs showed reasonable association but without statistical significance. Based on our data and those from previous reports, we proposed the C allele for rs2074192, the T allele for ACE2 rs233574, and the C allele of AGT as risk factor for obesity and COVID-19 severity, although the association with obesity was shown only in female subjects while the association with COVID-19 severity was shown only in male subjects. We also proposed two haplotypes, rs2074192-rs233574-rs699 (CC-TT-CC in females, and C-T-CC) as risky combination for COVID-19 severity, while two haplotypes (TT-CC-TT in females, and T-C-TT in males) as protective. Two main limitations in our study; first is the small number of studied subjects which might have obscured significant associations. The second limitation is related to the retrospective type of our study that did not allow us to follow up with subject clinical outcomes

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